

Managing Diversity in Business Education: A Case of Dubai International Academic City (DIAC)

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ABSTRACT: Education is an important factor in developing any nation around the world. Today's developed countries are much focused on education in varied fields. This has become possible through meaningful diversity in every field. Latest developments & innovations are the backbone to compete in today's competitive world. Best business education in Europe & North American countries have opened avenues of competition for other nations. These initiatives of being accredited by AACSB is a clear direction for successful business schools. UAE has been a preferred destination for more than two hundred nationalities who are working in different fields. Such diversity is the reason of varied developments in almost every domain. The educational projects, research based initiatives, business forums and meetings made it possible to get exponential growth in UAE and Dubai in particular. Dubai is one of the most demanded place to live and work in different companies & universities. Referring to this case research, education is the most focused area and set as top priority of government's projects for 2020. There are few AACSB accredited Business Schools in UAE and others are trying best to get it done through varied skills as possible through diversified opportunities in Dubai. Dubai is leading in education sector in the region where all nationalities are working and being educated in multiple fields. Dubai's diversity has made it much attractive to be educated in the multicultural city.

KEYWORDS: diversity, business education, business schools, different cultures and international standards

Introduction

Government has taken lucrative initiatives to maintain such environment of diversity and growing each day. It is great opportunity for education sector through diversity as set up in DIAC. The purpose of this research is to report on the essentials of diversity in Business schools. Teaching through case situations has become a challenge especially in today's diversified age. Business Faculty should be equipped with diversity exposure to transform the same to students who are more inclined to diversify phenomena. The purpose of writing such situations is to offer some practical suggestions to adopt a diversified approach of teaching in order to have a salutary effect on students' learning. The Case situations are specially developed to help students and faculty to enhance their exposure with required exposure. The purpose of this research is to write mini comparative cases to enhance students' capability to understand the diversified culture in order to plan & operate good business. The simple design based on descriptive aspects with case study approach. The proposed case situations will have a greater practical implication on Business schools and organizations in modern times.

Table 1. (Managing diversity & its impact)

Ministry of Education, UAE KHDA (Knowledge & Human Development Authority) DIAC (Dubai International Academic City)	
<u>Managing diversity</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversified Culture • Business Education • Human Development • Business Opportunities • <u>Diversity programs</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Sharing diversified exposure ○ Exchange of varied experience ○ Impactful education 	<u>Impact of Diversity on Business Education</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research • Collaboration • Intellectual Capital • Mini Cases / Mini Stories • Short videos / Small Posters / • Small groups / Brief demos • Writing half page cases
Diversity in Professional and Ethical Education	

Methodology

This research will also offer mini situations on diversified culture that becomes the reason to achieve business development in the particular region. This is well supported by the accurate guidance in form of diversity exposure in business schools. This research has developed such case studies to cover the contents and regions as mentioned above. Teaching is a great art that is earned through student centric approach. The rapid pace of technological aspects made everything available but still lack expertise in certain fields but diversity in education has filled such gap with effective initiatives on quality education & diversified learning experiences. This means that diversity background made difference in effective educational programs. This is a case study research that also investigates about the Diversity in Education (Diversity refers to many nationalities living in UAE with special focus on Dubai). The purpose of this research is to see and explore the different aspects of diversity in Education (different nationalities, different approaches, and different methods of teaching, different technological approaches in teaching and learning)

Research Question

- Which Business schools have more diversity and why?
- How such diversity is managed in Dubai, UAE?
- How HR managers and Deans evaluate the diversified Faculty in Business Schools

Findings and Propositions

The research has found diversity as most important aspect in modern times. The result showed that Dubai is increasing the diversity aspect at phenomenal pace. The research has found that the learning methods, delivery, research and educational leadership have been very effective due to diversity initiatives & programs. Few propositions on diversity are mentioned in the case study. The research proposed a diversity framework that showed the hierarchical activities on diversity. This proposed framework is just a sequential process to maintain educational standards.

Expected Contribution

This research will be beneficial for government officials who supported educational institutions. This will also help policy makers, VCs and other relevant authorities. The research has shown a

diversity framework that can be a guiding note for educational heads at varied Universities. This research will market the importance of diversity in educational sector. The Diversity aspects will ensure varied styles in teaching & learning.

- Successful educational setup
- Blended methods
- Technology integration
- Practical Case methods
- Interactive sessions
- Faculty exposure & development
- Students' development initiatives
- Governmental support & guidance
- Quality of standards & criteria
- International advisory boards

Brief on Mini Case example

Dubai Business School, University of Dubai has been accredited by AACSB. Before such accreditation, this university had approximate more than 5000 enrolments and still is growing after high standards of AACSB. This prestigious accreditation has gained not only same enrolment but increasing more as demand of quality students are lined up to make an entry into such reputable Business School. More will be covered in the detailed case study.

Brief on Data source

1. DIAC: <http://www.diacedu.ae/about/about-diac/>

The world's largest free zone dedicated to higher education and the pursuit of intellectual growth: Dubai International Academic City (DIAC) was launched in April 2007 to cater to the needs of the region's growing and diverse academic community. Home to numerous regional and international colleges and universities, it serves over 24,000 students from all around the world. With more than 400 undergraduate and post-graduate programs currently offered to students, DIAC continues to expand and grow as per the needs of its robust and talented academic community (<http://www.diacedu.ae/about/about-diac/>)

2. DUBAI: <http://www.diacedu.ae/about/about-dubai/>

The tertiary sector in Dubai is comprised of International Branch Campuses (IBCs) as well as local Universities funded by the federal government. The UAE itself has the highest number of International Branch Campuses of any country in the world, with nearly 40 in the UAE out of over 220 worldwide. The UAE is growing as an education hub with many international higher education institutions setting up here, catering to transactional students from across the world. The increase in transactional students can be attributed to the rise in educational tourism placing UAE as a global tourist destination and focus on international attention. With Dubai expecting a growth in tourist numbers at 7-9% annually, the rise of educational tourism towards emerging markets will play a big part in this shift (<http://www.diacedu.ae/about/about-dubai/>)

Clarity note: This is just an extended abstract and considered for this particular Conference. The Case study paper is still in progress and more explanation on results will be added in full paper.